

FUNCTIONAL AND SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF THE TRANSLATION OF ENGLISH ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

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Abstract. As teaching of vocabulary is an important task in second language acquisition and translation so the article is intended to cover major issues pertaining to abbreviations: “hidden” semantics, correlation with words, interaction with a context, historical aspects. National and international markers are discussed as actual extra linguistic factors. The article is based on the methodological assumption that foreign language acquisition is treated as a means of forming professional competence of specialists. The donating role of English in abbreviation process is stated. Abbreviations are not artificially created linguistic units for language economy but they eliminate contradiction between modern consciousness and limited lexical resources of any language. Abbreviation semantics represents a complex phenomenon; to study it, we need data taken from other sciences, the formation of abbreviation semantics takes place in parallel with the abbreviation process. The authors’ analysis of phonetic, grammatical and morphological peculiarities of abbreviations is reported.

Keywords: abbreviation; semantics; context; language universal.

1. Introduction.

Everyone recognizes that learning is enhanced when students are presented with lessons that engage their interest. The modern world contains an abundance of information that is represented with abbreviation for pragmatic purposes. Abbreviations are language universals; their nominative function is increasing as they give novel names to well known notions and objects. Abbreviations correlate with words but they are not equipollent though they have many common features. Semantic structure of abbreviations is complicated with specific connotations. The context-level of studying discloses the “hidden” semantics of abbreviations. Different types of contexts are defined (macro and micro contexts; compensatory, intensifying). Abbreviations are not only of linguistic value but also of historical as they may contain archaic elements, being formed with ancient models of contraction. Abbreviations are not artificially created linguistic units for language economy but they eliminate the contradiction between the modern consciousness and limited lexical resources of any language. Studying/ teaching abbreviation as a practical aim it demands theoretical background because the deeper a teacher knows the problem the clearer he/she can articulate the explanation. The article answers students’ frequently asked questions: whether abbreviations are words; how to choose the proper translation for homonymic abbreviations; when and why this linguistic units appeared etc.

Semantics of linguistic units, although there are many papers on this issue, is up to now one of the deepest and most enigmatic fields of linguistics. A particular interest is shown in semantics of abbreviations of the English language serving as one of current main sources to borrow abbreviations for other languages, although it aggressively borrowed abbreviation from other languages in the past. As abbreviations are information cumulative linguistic units, they may be

presented in various types, given a wide approach to abbreviation, in syllabic, compound syllabic and initial ones and semantic processes within each type are due to a qualitative and quantitative composition of basic units, features of their functioning and a width of a semantic range of a formant. Abbreviations cannot be treated as created artificially in view of linguistic economy or as “play on words”. A nominative function of abbreviations has become a current important linguistic and social mission. They denote new concepts and real objects and, thus, enrich the language.

2. Main part.

Abbreviations eliminate a contradiction between needs for thinking and limited lexical resources of the language. Abbreviations having a lexical synonym differ from it in terms of not only orthography, but also stylistics. It is natural that opinions of linguists differ as to a range of problems of abbreviation. “Abbreviation is not a random phenomenon, it is not a “damage of the language”, a fancy of some people, but an objective regular process stipulated by changes in needs for communication due to development of society and internal patterns of development of the language”. As a large majority of abbreviations relate to a human being and various spheres of its activities, a human factor plays a significant role in creation of abbreviations and is crucial to form semantics, because only a human being can “put” a meaning in words. As Lipatov wrote, “You cannot but admit that every developed language of the world, including Russian, has abbreviations. They cannot suddenly arise in the language ready for use, like Athena from Zeus’s head!”. As for the English language, we may note that it serves as a “donor” of abbreviations. If, according to Lipatov’s statement, “Russia became the very melting pot where all world languages (and, first of all, European ones) formed their new, “abbreviation” image: thus, an abbreviation “bud” originated in Russia developed into a magnificent flower – shortening of words with all its semantic and word formation components”, the English language may be qualified as a modern “guide” of Latin-based international abbreviation on a global scale.

Abbreviations are units included in a vocabulary, and the abbreviation process is a universal way of word formation, mainly for a reason that abbreviations are deemed as equivalents of words or as linguistic units, which correlate with words. Therefore, the theory of equivalence of abbreviations to words deserves a special study. The term “equivalent of the word” was created by Shcherba. He stressed that such group of words denoted one concept and was a potential equivalent of the word. Words and abbreviations are introduced into speech as they are. This fact may be given as one of arguments for the theory of equivalence. Such introduction into speech is characteristic of all linguistic units, and it is not practical to consider them as equivalents of words. It is just important to factor in characteristics of reproducibility in a ready state depending on features of structures and semantics of different units of the language. As for the structure and semantics, abbreviations are units of the language written with no spaces, but they are much more complex than words, and this has an effect on their meaning in a written or oral context. A real fundamental sign of a word is its ability to name. At the same time, this sign is not self-sufficient, because it is characteristic of both words and word combinations and sentences, however, it is a (content) word that shows to the fullest extent its ability to name and clearly represents it. Naming is described as a three-component universal and logical relation of a semantic triangle: thought-symbol object (referent), all components in their linguistic representation are enriched with features characteristic of a linguistic view of the world. Acts of naming are products of the speech, and their results are used by a language system, functional and social norms of the language and usage. An abbreviation unit has its ability to name, as in this case a three-component relation, thought-symbol-object (referent), is evident: an abbreviation, being a symbol, names an object having categorical properties of a formed concept. Any lexical abbreviation or a word in any language may serve as an example. According to the theory of equivalence, abbreviations may be considered as lexical units which do not need a special classification attributable to them, and they should be classified the same as words. Thus, a specific character of abbreviations is diminished. A word, no matter how complex its semantic structure is, differs from abbreviations. Abbreviations and words have

common features, but this should not be more prominent than the specific character of abbreviations. Therefore, it is practical to consider abbreviation units not as equivalents of words, but as linguistic units which correlate with words. When studying the correlation of abbreviations with a word structure in a pragmatic aspect, we should adopt an integrated approach to take into account semantic, stylistic, structural, grammar and accentological features of abbreviations and words objectively.

“The real significance of linguistic units is one of the most difficult aspects in language teaching. It is rather difficult to define the meaning of a word as it is connected with many lingual and extra lingual aspects – logical and psychological, historical and philosophical”. In view of a complex semantic structure of abbreviations and high specific weight of a connotation of many abbreviations, we should study abbreviations in a context. Besides, abbreviations, being stable and written with no spaces, may be variously transformed in terms of their structure and semantics, including complicated transformations, which are impossible in words. Only the context may help us to monitor semantic development of abbreviations and conveying of potential senses of an abbreviation’s meaning. Any occasional changes, prior to be fixed in the language, are implemented in speech in a written or oral generative context.

Abbreviations represent not only a linguistic interest, but also a historical interest, as some abbreviations keep archaic elements conveying features of past epochs. For example, the abbreviation GOLF (Gentlemen Only Ladies Forbidden) is given in dictionaries, it reflects a prohibition on participation of women in golf; now both women and men may play golf. Ancient models of contraction were (and are) used to create new abbreviations and simplify existing ones, as they appropriately convey semantics of an original. The study of abbreviations in a diachronic aspect proves its language universal, as all languages contain abbreviations, abbreviations are found not only in “living languages”, but also in “dead ones”, for example, in Latin.

Phonetic, orthographic, morphological, grammatical features of abbreviated units influence semantic processes which predetermine functioning of abbreviated units in oral and written speeches. The following features are very significant in language teaching process. Abbreviated units are pronounced according to laws of a current English discourse. For example, *crg.* [ˈkæridʒ] [carriage]; *bkd* (booked) [ˈbʊkt]; *lt* (light) [laɪt], *TESSA*, *Tessa* [ˈtesə] [tax-exempt special savings account). Abbreviated units are subject to laws of language development, mainly pronounced as words, and their orthography is transformed, abbreviation semantics is formed similar to word semantics. As a rule, to form abbreviated units, elements of original units, which ensure convenient pronunciation of abbreviated units, are used. For example, *SALLY* [ˈsæli] (Small-scale Alternative Location Licence), *VALUE* [ˈvælju:] – (Specific Programme for the Dissemination and Utilization of Scientific and Technological Research Results), *TEMPUS* [ˈtempʊs] (TransEuropean Mobility Programme for University Studies). Orthography of abbreviated units has close ties with lexicography; it is a graphical presentation of an abbreviated unit which predetermines its place in a dictionary. There are several ways of writing English abbreviated units. Abbreviated units are written as one word, several words, in capital or small letters. Abbreviations may contain dots, slashes, division signs, etc. For example, *L/D* (letter of deposit), *W.P.A.* (with particular average), *V-STOL* (vertical and short take off and landing (aircraft)), *oxdic*, *B2B* (business to customer). Abbreviated units may correlate with various parts of speech (nouns, adjectives, verbs) and perform their grammatical categories. Abbreviated units categorized as nouns are divided into proper and common nouns. Proper nouns: *WTC* (William Thomas Consgrave), *TO* (Terrell Owens), *VVP* (Vladimir Vladimirovich Putin). Common nouns: *Emb* (Embassy), *St* (State). Abbreviated units categorized as common nouns are divided into countable and uncountable ones. Countable nouns: *Cand* (Candidate); *FSO* (Foreign Service Officer); *FP* (Federal Parliament). Uncountable nouns: *Auth* (Authority); *CI* (classified information); *Lib* (Liberalism). Moreover, abbreviated units categorized as nouns form semantic subcategories (it means that they denote animate and inanimate objects, abstract concepts). For example, *beg.* (beginning), *BBQ* (barbecue), *avia.* (aviation), *ent.* (entertainment).

3. Conclusion.

All the above aspects of abbreviations influence not only their form, but also their meaning. Thus, abbreviation semantics represents a complex phenomenon; to study it, we need data taken from other sciences – lexicology, grammar, stylistics, phonetics, history of the language, philosophy, history, logic, country studies, etc. The formation of abbreviation semantics takes place in parallel with the abbreviation process. Abbreviations exist in the language along with their interpretation ensuring naming of new sides of the reality perceived by a human being and giving “new” names to surrounding objects, events of the reality, etc. In some cases abbreviations are more popular than their interpretation and replace names of objects, properties, processes, conditions, situations, etc. For example, few people know that SMART is an abbreviation, and fewer people know its interpretation: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, Timed. A similar regularity exists in the Russian language, when abbreviations become the only names. For example, the abbreviation *ЖЗЛ* (the Office of Vital Records) is currently perceived by people as a word, many people do not know what it stands for. The fund of English abbreviations is very rich, has a centuries-old history and represents a complicated set of original and borrowed abbreviations, while original ones clearly prevail. Word formation by contracting is spread due to a general linguistic trend towards economy and attributed to a need for fixing new fragments of social experience using relevant short lexical means. The abbreviation process is one of ways corresponding with pragmatic purposes of word building. Rich content, a variety of functions and general availability of abbreviations make them convenient and compressed means of communication to the maximum extent.

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